

Firejail - A Human Tool to Control Software

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2017 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20170817> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

When we use a piece of software, we make an act of faith: Not only towards the developer but, above all, versus all other developers who put their hand on the various parts of the complex system that runs the software. When we acquire a piece of software, we tend to be cautious up to the Ethernet port, clumping firewalls, and scanners. Once off the net, in *our inner space*, we tend to fatally trust the software.

There are many ways to control almost every operation a software performs: Look for the different security models used in computer security, you will find the classic DAC, MAC, RBAC, along with other esoteric ones. For Linux, the *Discretionary Access Control* (DAC) has been superseded by the SELinux/AppArmor kernel extensions that support the *Mandatory Access Control* (MAC) mechanism: In the last years, both have been installed and activated by default in the major distributions. They can control a lot, but we can still move us through the whole garden.

To limit the garden, sandboxes have been created. A *sandbox*, basically, provides a high grade of program separation: Can separate file system, networks, resources, or can use virtualization, with more or less effort and control, depending on the security model based on.

3. Capabilities and seccomp Security Models

Capabilities security model focus on privileged users, splitting the bunch of permissions a super-user has in different portions, and assign one or more *labels* to a process to grant them the abilities to execute or access part of the OS. Think of capabilities as a bouquet of *accessible resources*, not just syscalls. As an example take a look at CAP_SYS_RAWIO (use man 7 capabilities):

```
CAP_SYS_RAWIO
* Perform I/O port operations (iop1(2) and
ioperm(2));
```

```
* access /proc/kcore;
* employ the FIBMAP ioctl(2) operation;
* open devices for accessing x86 model-
specific registers (MSRs, see msr(4));
* update /proc/sys/vm/mmap_min_addr;
* create memory mappings at addresses
below the value specified by
/proc/sys/vm/mmap_min_addr;
* map files in /proc/bus/pci;
* open /dev/mem and /dev/kmem;
* perform various SCSI device commands;
* perform certain operations on hpsa(4)
and cciss(4) devices;
* perform a range of device-specific
operations on other devices.
```

seccomp-bpf is an extension to *seccomp* that allows filtering of syscalls using a configurable policy implemented with Berkeley Packet Filter rules. It is used by OpenSSH and vsftpd as well as the Google Chrome/Chromium web browsers on Chrome OS and Linux. Is a kind of firewall to control which functionality, provided by the kernel (syscalls), a process can access, limiting the over exposure of the kernel itself versus a generic process. The number of syscalls may vary; on my system, 380/332[32/64] syscalls are supported (use man 2 syscalls and take a look into /usr/src/linux-headers-`<ver>`/include/uapi/asm-generic/unistd.h for a complete list).

4. Reducing Exposure

Firejail uses technologies like *Capabilities* [1] and *Seccomp-bpf* [2] to sandbox applications.

Take as an example the ping executable and try to reduce the exposure using the Firejail sandbox. We will:

1. Find out the syscalls ping uses
2. Drop all unneeded capabilities
3. Switch Firejail from syscalls blacklist to whitelist

As the first step, we try to find out the resources accessed by ping; dump the basic syscalls:

```
root@ubunthin:~# strace -qcf ping -c1 8.8.8.8
PING 8.8.8.8 (8.8.8.8) 56(84) bytes of data.
64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: icmp_seq=1 ttl=46
time=24.1 ms

--- 8.8.8.8 ping statistics ---
1 packets transmitted, 1 received, 0% packet
loss, time 0ms
rtt min/avg/max/mdev =
24.110/24.110/24.110/0.000 ms
```

```

% time      seconds  usecs/call   calls
errors syscall
-----
0.00  0.000000      0      8
read
0.00  0.000000      0      6
write
0.00  0.000000      0     35
13 open
0.00  0.000000      0     23
close
0.00  0.000000      0     23
fstat
0.00  0.000000      0     31
mmap
0.00  0.000000      0     14
mprotect
0.00  0.000000      0      1
munmap
0.00  0.000000      0      3
brk
0.00  0.000000      0      3
rt_sigaction
0.00  0.000000      0      1
rt_sigprocmask
0.00  0.000000      0      2
ioctl
0.00  0.000000      0      8
8 access
0.00  0.000000      0      1
setitimer
0.00  0.000000      0      1
getpid
0.00  0.000000      0      5
2 socket
0.00  0.000000      0      1
connect
0.00  0.000000      0      1
sendto
0.00  0.000000      0      1
recvmsg
0.00  0.000000      0      1
getsockname
0.00  0.000000      0      7
setsockopt
0.00  0.000000      0      1
getsockopt
0.00  0.000000      0      1
execve
0.00  0.000000      0      2
getuid
0.00  0.000000      0      1
setuid
0.00  0.000000      0      1
geteuid
0.00  0.000000      0      7
capget
0.00  0.000000      0      3
capset
0.00  0.000000      0      2
prctl
0.00  0.000000      0      1
arch_prctl
-----
100.00  0.000000      195
23 total

```

We can just start ping in Firejail without any specific profile or configuration, to have a minimum security gain. Per default, Firejail leaves all capabilities enabled but blacklists some syscalls:

```

root@ubunthin:/home/rcc# firejail --name=ping
ping 8.8.8.8

root@ubunthin:/home/rcc# firejail --list
11971:rcc:firejail --name=ping ping 8.8.8.8

```

```

root@ubunthin:/home/rcc# firejail --
seccomp.print=ping
SECCOMP Filter:
VALIDATE_ARCHITECTURE
EXAMINE_SYSCALL
UNKNOWN ENTRY!!!
UNKNOWN ENTRY!!!
UNKNOWN ENTRY!!!
BLACKLIST 165 mount
BLACKLIST 166 umount2
BLACKLIST 101 ptrace
BLACKLIST 246 kexec_load
BLACKLIST 320 kexec_file_load
BLACKLIST 304 open_by_handle_at
BLACKLIST 303 name_to_handle_at
BLACKLIST 175 init_module
BLACKLIST 313 finit_module
BLACKLIST 174 create_module
BLACKLIST 176 delete_module
BLACKLIST 172 iopl
BLACKLIST 173 ioperm
BLACKLIST 251 ioprio_set
BLACKLIST 167 swapon
BLACKLIST 168 swapoff
BLACKLIST 103 syslog
BLACKLIST 310 process_vm_readv
BLACKLIST 311 process_vm_writesv
BLACKLIST 139 sysfs
BLACKLIST 156 _sysctl
BLACKLIST 159 adjtimex
BLACKLIST 305 clock_adjtime
BLACKLIST 212 lookup_dcookie
BLACKLIST 298 perf_event_open
BLACKLIST 300 fanotify_init
BLACKLIST 312 kcmp
BLACKLIST 248 add_key
BLACKLIST 249 request_key
BLACKLIST 250 keyctl
BLACKLIST 134 uselib
BLACKLIST 163 acct
BLACKLIST 154 modify_ldt
BLACKLIST 155 pivot_root
BLACKLIST 206 io_setup
BLACKLIST 207 io_destroy
BLACKLIST 208 io_getevents
BLACKLIST 209 io_submit
BLACKLIST 210 io_cancel
BLACKLIST 216 remap_file_pages
BLACKLIST 237 mbind
BLACKLIST 239 get_mempolicy
BLACKLIST 238 set_mempolicy
BLACKLIST 256 migrate_pages
BLACKLIST 279 move_pages
BLACKLIST 278 vmsplice
BLACKLIST 161 chroot
BLACKLIST 184 tuxcall
BLACKLIST 169 reboot
BLACKLIST 180 nfsservctl
BLACKLIST 177 get_kernel_syms
RETURN_ALLOW

root@ubunthin:/home/rcc# firejail --
caps.print=ping
chown - enabled
dac_override - enabled
dac_read_search - enabled
fowner - enabled
fsetid - enabled
kill - enabled
setgid - enabled
setuid - enabled
setpcap - enabled
linux_immutable - enabled
net_bind_service - enabled
net_broadcast - enabled
net_admin - enabled
net_raw - enabled
ipc_lock - enabled
ipc_owner - enabled

```

```

sys_module - enabled
sys_rawio - enabled
sys_chroot - enabled
sys_ptrace - enabled
sys_pacct - enabled
sys_admin - enabled
sys_boot - enabled
sys_nice - enabled
sys_resource - enabled
sys_time - enabled
sys_tty_config - enabled
mknod - enabled
lease - enabled
audit_write - enabled
audit_control - enabled
setfcap - enabled
mac_override - enabled
mac_admin - enabled
syslog - enabled
wake_alarm - enabled
block_suspend - enabled
audit_read - enabled

```

Going through Capabilities, why should ping have the permission to create a filesystem node? Basically, we can drop all Capabilities up to CAP_NET_RAW, to remove access to all unneeded resources up to:

```

CAP_NET_RAW
* use RAW and PACKET sockets;
* bind to any address for transparent
proxying.

```

Just start Firejail:

```

root@ubunthin:/home/rcc# firejail --name=ping
--caps.keep=net_raw ping 8.8.8.8

root@ubunthin:/home/rcc# firejail --list
12121:rcc:firejail --name=ping --
caps.keep=net_raw ping 8.8.8.8

root@ubunthin:/home/rcc# firejail --
caps.print=ping
...
net_admin - disabled
net_raw - enabled
ipc_lock - disabled
...

```

We dropped all capabilities up to CAP_NET_RAW, forbidding at the same time access to many syscalls. But, since ping uses only 23 syscalls, we still are overexposed. With seccomp-bpf it is possible to fine filters and minimizes the syscalls used by ping, switching from blacklist to whitelist.

To whitelist the syscalls ping can use, start with the strace list of required syscalls and monitor the syslog for results:

```

root@ubunthin:/home/rcc# firejail --
caps.keep=net_raw --shell=none --noprofile --
debug --
seccomp.keep=read,write,open,close,fstat,mmap
,mprotect,munmap,brk,rt_sigaction,rt_sigprocm
ask,iocntl,access,setitimer,getpid,socket,conn
ect,sendto,recvmsg,getsockname,setsockopt,get
sockopt,execve,getuid,setuid,geteuid,capget,c
apset,prctl,arch_prctl,setresuid,setresgid,ge
tgid,fcntl,clone,set_robust_list,stat,nanosle
ep,wait4,getdents,exit_group ping -c1 8.8.8.8

```

Syslog reports the last syscall causing a problem (blocked by Firejail):

```

Aug 7 21:09:57 ubunthin firejail[28419]:
firejail --shell=none --noprofile --

```

```

seccomp.keep=read,write,open,close,fstat,mmap
,mprotect,munmap,brk,rt_sigaction,rt_sigprocm
ask,iocntl,access,setitimer,getpid,socket,conn
ect,sendto,recvmsg,getsockname,setsockopt,get
sockopt,execve,getuid,setuid,geteuid,capget,c
apset,prctl,arch_prctl,setresuid,setresgid,ge
tgid,fcntl --debug ping -c1 8.8.8.8
Aug 7 21:09:58 ubunthin kernel:
[98202.176765] audit: type=1326
audit(1502132998.041:55): auid=1000 uid=0
gid=0 ses=2 pid=28420 comm="firejail"
exe="/usr/bin/firejail" sig=31 arch=c000003e
syscall=56 compat=0 ip=0x7ff72e5ca40a
code=0x0
Aug 7 21:09:58 ubunthin firejail[28419]:
exiting...

```

In this case, ping tried to access syscall 56, which is not whitelisted, causing Firejail to kill the process. To find out the syscall name, from syscall number:

```

root@ubunthin:/home/rcc# firejail --debug-
syscalls | grep 56
56 - clone

```

Update the syscall whitelist with clone and retry at the end, to the initial strace list, we added setresuid,setresgid,getgid,fcntl,clone,set_robust_list,stat,nanosleep,wait4,getdents,exit_group:

```

root@ubunthin:/home/rcc# firejail --
caps.keep=net_raw --shell=none --noprofile --
debug --
seccomp.keep=read,write,open,close,fstat,mmap
,mprotect,munmap,brk,rt_sigaction,rt_sigprocm
ask,iocntl,access,setitimer,getpid,socket,conn
ect,sendto,recvmsg,getsockname,setsockopt,get
sockopt,execve,getuid,setuid,geteuid,capget,c
apset,prctl,arch_prctl,setresuid,setresgid,ge
tgid,fcntl,clone,set_robust_list,stat,nanosle
ep,wait4,getdents,exit_group ping -c1 8.8.8.8
Command name #ping#
DISPLAY :0, 0
Enabling IPC namespace
Using the local network stack
Parent pid 28503, child pid 28504
The new log directory is
/proc/28504/root/var/log
Initializing child process
Host network configured
PID namespace installed
Mounting tmpfs on /run/firejail/mnt directory
Mounting read-only /bin, /sbin, /lib, /lib32,
/lib64, /usr, /etc, /var
Mounting tmpfs on /dev/shm
Mounting tmpfs on /var/lock
Mounting tmpfs on /var/tmp
Mounting tmpfs on /var/log
Mounting tmpfs on /var/lib/dhcp
Mounting tmpfs on /var/lib/snmp
Mounting tmpfs on /var/lib/sudo
Create the new utmp file
Mount the new utmp file
Remounting /proc and /proc/sys filesystems
Remounting /sys directory
Disable /sys/firmware
Disable /sys/hypervisor
Disable /sys/module
Disable /sys/power
Disable /sys/kernel/debug
Disable /sys/kernel/vmcoreinfo
Disable /sys/kernel/uevent_helper
Disable /proc/sys/fs/binfmt_misc
Disable /proc/sys/kernel/core_pattern
Disable /proc/sys/kernel/modprobe
Disable /proc/sysrq-trigger
Disable /proc/sys/kernel/hotplug
Disable /proc/sys/vm/panic_on_oom

```

```

Disable /proc/irq
Disable /proc/bus
Disable /proc/sched_debug
Disable /proc/timer_list
Disable /proc/timer_stats
Disable /proc/kcore
Disable /proc/kallsyms
Disable /lib/modules
Disable /usr/lib/debug
Disable /boot
Disable /dev/port
Disable /sys/fs
DISPLAY :0, 0
Set caps filter 2000
Ending syscall filter
SECCOMP Filter:
  VALIDATE_ARCHITECTURE
  EXAMINE_SYSCALL
  UNKNOWN ENTRY!!!
  UNKNOWN ENTRY!!!
  UNKNOWN ENTRY!!!
  WHITELIST 105 setuid
  WHITELIST 106 setgid
  WHITELIST 116 setgroups
  WHITELIST 32 dup
  WHITELIST 0 read
  WHITELIST 1 write
  WHITELIST 2 open
  WHITELIST 3 close
  WHITELIST 5 fstat
  WHITELIST 9 mmap
  WHITELIST 10 mprotect
  WHITELIST 11 munmap
  WHITELIST 12 brk
  WHITELIST 13 rt_sigaction
  WHITELIST 14 rt_sigprocmask
  WHITELIST 16 ioctl
  WHITELIST 21 access
  WHITELIST 38 setitimer
  WHITELIST 39 getpid
  WHITELIST 41 socket
  WHITELIST 42 connect
  WHITELIST 44 sendto
  WHITELIST 47 recvmsg
  WHITELIST 51 getsockname
  WHITELIST 54 setsockopt
  WHITELIST 55 getsockopt
  WHITELIST 59 execve
  WHITELIST 102 getuid
  WHITELIST 105 setuid
  WHITELIST 107 geteuid
  WHITELIST 125 capget
  WHITELIST 126 capset
  WHITELIST 157 prctl
  WHITELIST 158 arch_prctl
  WHITELIST 117 setresuid
  WHITELIST 119 setresgid
  WHITELIST 104 getgid
  WHITELIST 72 fcntl
  WHITELIST 56 clone
  WHITELIST 273 set_robust_list
  WHITELIST 4 stat
  WHITELIST 35 nanosleep
  WHITELIST 61 wait4
  WHITELIST 78 getdents
  WHITELIST 231 exit_group
  KILL_PROCESS
Save seccomp filter, size 784 bytes
seccomp enabled
Username root, no supplementary groups
starting application
LD_PRELOAD=(null)
execvp argument 0: ping
execvp argument 1: -c1
execvp argument 2: 8.8.8.8
Child process initialized
PING 8.8.8.8 (8.8.8.8) 56(84) bytes of data.
monitoring pid 2

64 bytes from 8.8.8.8: icmp_seq=1 ttl=45

```

```

time=28.6 ms

--- 8.8.8.8 ping statistics ---
1 packets transmitted, 1 received, 0% packet
loss, time 0ms
rtt min/avg/max/mdev =
28.614/28.614/28.614/0.000 ms
Sandbox monitor: waitpid 2 retval 2 status 0

Parent is shutting down, bye...

```

Now we can create a profile for the ping application that minimizes the system exposure. If ping tries to make some other calls, or access some other resources, it will be immediately killed.

5. Where and when using Firejail

Security In-Depth paradigm requires multiple layers of security controls so that if one fails, another can take over.

Firejail can be used as an additional line of defense, especially for internet browsers. Comes with a bunch of predefined profiles and is relatively easy to configure additional applications.

I use Firejail for browsing, for software analysis, to use specific temporary settings (like specific DNS), to simulate installation and so on.

6. Sandboxes vs. Containers

The difference between sandboxes and containers can be reduced to the filesystem:

A sandbox works on an existing filesystem, a container has a separate filesystem.

The security focus of the technologies is different:

Sandboxing is fully focused on security, while containers on virtualization/developing.

In any case, since the used security model is the same, having confidence with seccomp-bpf and Capabilities will also help a lot in understanding a securing container environments (aka Docker).

7. Summary

Securing a computer does not end at the Ethernet port. Once installed and trusted, a piece of code is basically free to access a lot of resources not really necessary (think of X).

This overexposure has become critical with container technology, where the border between the resources and virtual resources may be very confusing.

Using Firejail is a quick-win for each application, especially for browsers without sandboxing. It is easy to use and configure, and the impact on the system is very small.

8. Tools

Other tools to try:

- *Trinity: Linux system call fuzzer* [3]
- *syscall_limiter* [4]
- *Google nsjail* [5]
- *Filesystem Sandbox for Linux* [6]
- *nextgen – A Genetic File, Syscall and Network Fuzzer* [7]

9. External Links

- [1] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Capability-based_security
- [2] https://www.kernel.org/doc/Documentation/prctl/seccomp_filter.txt
- [3] <https://github.com/kernelslacker/trinity>
- [4] https://github.com/vi/syscall_limiter
- [5] <https://github.com/google/nsjail>
- [6] <https://github.com/adtac/fssb>
- [7] <https://github.com/hbowden/nextgen>